

dirty color led to prediction of heavy losses, but the spikelets later filled. The table shows GLD incidence on various cultivars.

Isolations on PDA from affected glumes and grains showed *C. lunata* (in

80% discolored grains) and *F. semitectum* (5%). Unlike in the 1978 wet season, *C. lunata* was prominent.

Inoculating *C. lunata* on emerged panicles by spraying and dipping, and on the boot stage by injecting spore or

mycelial suspensions on three dates produced symptoms of dirty panicle on almost all glumes and grains. *F. semitectum* did not produce discoloration by any of the tested inoculation procedures. ■

Survival of sclerotia of *Corticium sasakii* at different soil depths

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Sclerotia of *Corticium sasakii* (Shirai) Matsumoto — the rice sheath blight fungus — were grown on sterilized rice grain for 1½ months and then placed in a layer of 5, 10, and 15 cm deep soil respectively, in clay pots. On 17 August 1978, the pots were buried in a highland where the level of the soil of the pot and that of the field were the same. The soil in the pot contained 0.336% organic

carbon, 0.09% N, 57.3 kg available P₂O₅/ha, 1,111.5 kg available K₂O/ha and pH 6.95. The sclerotia with the soil mass from the different depths were taken out at monthly intervals, starting

Viability of sclerotia of *C. sasakii* buried at different soil depths (observation from 15 sclerotia), Assam, India.

Observation time (mo after start of study)	Viability of sclerotia (%) at soil depth of		
	5 cm	10cm	15 cm
3	1	1	2
4	1	1	1
6	1	1	2
7	2	2	2
8	1	2	1

at 3 months of burial, and retrieved by washing over a mesh. These were then surface-sterilized with mercuric chloride and viability was tested by growing them on potato dextrose agar mixed with streptomycin sulfate.

The table shows that the viability of sclerotia dropped considerably after 3 months (first observation) and remained almost the same, regardless of the depth of burial, up to 8 months (last observation). Sclerotia from the different soil depths were found to be colonized by different organisms including *Trichoderma viride*, but those retrieved from below 5 cm were colonized most and those from below 15 cm least. ■

Effect of seed treatment with fungicides in improving germination of sheath rot-infected seeds

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Sheath rot disease of rice caused by *Sarocladium attenuatum* Gams and Hawkworth caused grain discoloration of seeds in varieties ADT31, Bhavani, CO39, and CO40. In all four varieties, 45% of seeds died before emergence and seedlings that survived were about 30% (Table 1).

Six fungicides were tested for their efficiency in the control of seed germination failure. For each treatment 50 g seeds showing infection symptoms was

Table 1. Data on germination^a of 4 varieties, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Pre-emergence death (no.)	Post-emergence death (no.)	Seedlings that survived (no.)
ADT31	45	24	31
Bhavani	42	26	32
CO39	45	30	25
CO40	41	29	30

^aMean of 3 replications.

Table 2. Effect of fungicide seed treatment on germination. Tamil Nadu, India.

Fungicide	Germination ^a (%)	
	Immediately after seed treatment	After 6 mo storage
TMTD	60 (51)	47 (43)
Captan	72 (58)	56 (48)
Agrosan	66 (54)	52 (46)
Panoctine	75 (60)	67 (55)
Panoram	55 (48)	43 (41)
Benomyl	82 (65)	76 (61)
Control	44 (42)	24 (30)
SED	4.06	2.38
CD (P = 0.05)	8.72	(P = 0.05) 5.11

^aMean of 3 replications. Figures in parentheses are transformed values.

treated with fungicides at 2 g or 2 ml/kg seed. The seeds were then sown in pots containing 2 kg sterilized wetland soil. Untreated infected seeds were sown as the control. Another set of seeds treated with fungicides was stored in the laboratory at 25± 1°C for 6 months, then tested for germination 10 days after sowing.

Benomyl and panoctine improved seed germination best, both immediately after the treatment and after 6 months storage (Table 2). ■

Influence of diammonium phosphate on brown spot disease of rice

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Brown spot of rice caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* is very severe at the seedling stage during *navarai* (Nov-Mar) and *thaladi* (Oct-Feb) seasons. A field experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with four replications during 1979 *navarai*. IR20, which is susceptible to brown leaf spot disease, was raised in a 5- x 2-m plot. Diammonium phosphate (DAP) was applied to the nursery and disease incidence was observed. The treatments were: 1) wet seed treatment with DAP at 0.5% for 10 hours; 2) sprouted seed treatment with DAP at 0.5% for 30 minutes; 3) basal dressing of 500 g DAP/10 m²; 4) topdressing of 500 g DAP/10 m² on the 7th day; 5) topdressing of 500 g DAP/10 m² on the 15th day; 6) foliar spraying with 0.5% DAP on the 7th day; 7) foliar spraying with 0.5% DAP on the 15th day; 8) topdressing of 500 g DAP/10 m² on the

20th day; 9) untreated control. The disease count was taken on the 30th day after sowing. All the modes of application of DAP on the rice nursery significantly reduced seedling infection

by the brown spot pathogen. Among the treatments, topdressing of 500 g DAP/10 m² on the 7th day was highly effective in eliminating seedling infection. It resulted in healthy and vigorous rice

seedlings. The results indicated that the brown spot disease at the seedling stage can be controlled by application of DAP. ■

Yellow wilt of rice in the lower Amazon Basin, Brazil

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In mechanical cultivation of irrigated rice in the lower Amazon Basin, the yellow wilt problem of the rice plant was first noted in a few commercial rice-producing fields during the second crop season of 1978. The disorder became more serious during the first and second crop seasons of 1979. The rice variety IR22 was commercially grown in the varzea marshland soils.

In most cases, the growth of the rice plant proceeded normally till 1 to 2 weeks before the flowering-milk stages. After these stages, the older leaves started dying off rapidly while the younger leaves turned yellow-brown and gradually died back from the tips. About 1 to 2 weeks before harvest, a sudden withering of the yellow-brown leaves occurred. Ripening was accelerated and at harvest the affected plants looked dehydrated, dirty, weak and droopy without a single green or light yellow leaf. Such a crop had many decayed and

dead roots and was usually accompanied by an attack by *Helminthosporium* leaf spot and/ or *Cercospora* leaf spot and/ or *Pyricularia* neck blast and/ or *Rhizoctonia* sheath blight. However, such attacks appeared to be secondary. The low photosynthetic activity of the leaves and the poor root system resulted in a low grain yield. Because the leaves dried and died before maturation and the same panicle contained green as well as ripe grains, it was hard to determine the appropriate time for harvesting. The grain quality was usually poor. In some cases, where the disorder occurred before the flowering stage, the growth of the rice plant was poor, a yellow-brown discoloration appeared on the tips of green leaves and the older leaves dried and died starting from the tips. At the flowering stage the panicles varied in height and few leaves remained green. The withering of leaves proceeded more quickly and was accelerated by drainage for harvesting. Such a symptom occurred mostly on the plants grown in the low organic soils. The name "yellow wilt" was used because of the yellowing and wilt symptoms.

A combination of factors including iron toxicity, potassium deficiency and incidence of *Helminthosporium* leaf spot and/ or *Cercospora* leaf spot and/ or *Pyricularia* neck blast and/ or *Rhizoctonia* sheath blight diseases is suspected as the possible main cause of yellow wilt. Recent studies have demonstrated that the yellow wilt disorder is associated with potassium deficiency in the soil solution and the low potassium content of the plants. Increase in the supply of potassium fertilizer from the previously recommended 20–30 kg/ ha to the presently recommended 70–90 kg/ ha and use of split potassium application technique have noticeably alleviated the disorder. Three tentative remedies having been recommended for the disorder include: 1) submergence of the varzea marshland soils for at least 1 month before planting; 2) increase in the supply of potassium fertilizer up to 70–90 kg/ ha and use of split potassium application; and 3) application of higher amount of potassium fertilizer at about maximum tillering stage but avoidance of excessive nitrogen dressing at this stage. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Effect of storage time on insecticide-treated rice seeds

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Insecticide treatment of rice seed has several advantages and has application for direct-seeded rice (dryland or wetland) and transplanted rice in the seedbed. Insecticides considered for seed treatment should satisfy certain requirements before recommendation; the most important is that they must not adversely

affect germination of seeds or the seedlings. Sometimes seed are not sown immediately after treatment, so we measured the effect of storage on germination in an experiment from July to September 1979 with eight insecticides—carbofuran, bendiocarb, phenthoate, chlorthiophos, methoxychlor, cartap, formetanate, and promecarb. A 25% gum arabic water solution (sticker) was added to IR36 seeds in a plastic bag and the seeds were hand-agitated until the surfaces were evenly coated. Insecticides were then added at 10 g a.i./kg and the seeds were agitated again to ensure uni-

form coverage. The treated seeds were then dried in the shade and stored for 8 weeks in a nonairconditioned room (temp, 28–30°C; relative humidity, 80%). Germination percentage was taken at weekly intervals by placing 25 seeds in petri dishes on filter paper with moistened cotton wads. Each treatment was replicated four times and arranged in a completely randomized design.

All insecticides showed phytotoxicity up to 8 weeks after treatment (see table). Chlorthiophos, promecarb, and bendiocarb had immediate phytotoxic effects on seeds germinated on the same day